

Preliminary version of a confidence index

C3S2_370_MF – Operational production of seasonal forecasts

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1. Executive summary

As part of WP4 of the C3S2_370_MF contract dedicated to innovative products, Météo-France (MF) has committed to design a real-time confidence index for seasonal forecasts (Task 4.3), to be computed every time a new forecast is issued. The aim of the confidence index is to indicate users whether the forecast is informative or not, in terms of climate conditions over Europe.

This milestone introduces two approaches currently under investigation to create the confidence index. The first approach is intended to be applicable to the forecast of any parameter consisting in a single value, e.g a grid-point or box-averaged physical variable. It relates confidence to the maximum probability of forecast tercile categories. The second approach is designed to indicate the confidence in the forecast of a full spatial pattern. A possible methodology for this second approach is based on the projection of the real-time forecast on specific patterns called Predictable Components, that the forecasting system is supposed to predict accurately. While the first approach for single values is easy to implement and can be applied to many forecasting problems, the second approach for spatial patterns is appealing in the context of seasonal forecast bulletins when a synthesis map of the expected climate conditions over Europe is produced.

In this milestone, both approaches are developed and tested for near-surface temperature over Europe. Our future plans for this task include improvements and refinement of the proposed approaches, as well as implementation on other variables (starting with precipitation) and/or combinations of variables.

2. Introduction

Seasonal forecast bulletins issued on a monthly basis by Météo-France include synthesis maps of Europe highlighting areas where there is a signal for anomalous conditions over the next season, for both near-surface temperature (T2M) and precipitation (RR). The synthesis maps are designed by forecasters, based on the numerical forecasts provided by the Copernicus Climate Change Services (C3S) combined with expert knowledge. The use of expert knowledge is an illustration of users trying to determine how trustworthy the numerical outputs are, and adjusting them accordingly.

Such an approach might greatly benefit from additional diagnostics about how accurate the forecast is expected to be. In order to address this point, we propose to design a confidence index that can be provided in real-time when a forecast is issued. The idea behind the confidence index is to give *a priori* indications of forecast performance, in line with the expression “forecasting forecast skill” coined by Tennekes et al (1986). Moreover, such a confidence index is intended to be related with “windows of opportunity” (Mariotti et al, 2020) of seasonal prediction, when specific drivers make forecasts better than average.

The idea of “forecasting the forecast skill” has already been explored several times in the context of numerical weather forecasting at short-to-medium range. Studies such as Kalnay and Dalcher (1987), Palmer and Tibaldi (1988), Chen (1989), Molteni and Palmer (1991) or Wobus and Kalnay

(1995) have proposed statistical schemes (e.g linear regressions) predicting the root mean square error and/or the anomaly correlation coefficient (i.e spatial correlation) of forecasts of 500 hPa geopotential height over hemispheric or regional domains. Moreover, Météo-France also issues a confidence index for the day-4 to day-9 forecasts over France, with values ranging from 1 (no confidence in the forecast) to 5 (perfect confidence in the forecast) determined empirically by operational forecasters using the ensemble forecasts available (Météo-France, 2020). From all these works, we retain that *a priori* confidence in a forecast may arise from several principles:

- Agreement among forecasts from different modelling centres, or agreement among members from the same ensemble forecast (Kalnay and Dalcher 1987, Leslie and Holland 1990, Wobus and Kalnay 1995, Météo-France operational confidence index)
- Amplitude of the forecast anomalies (Molteni and Palmer 1991, Wobus and Kalnay 1995)
- Stability of consecutive forecasts valid over the same period (Chen 1989, Leslie and Holland 1990, Météo-France operational confidence index)
- Persistence along the forecast, from the initial conditions to the target lead time (Wobus and Kalnay 1995)

These studies focus on numerical weather prediction and therefore provide a forecast skill prediction at daily lead times. However, even though our current target in seasonal forecasting is the next trimester, most of the above mentioned principles still hold true and can therefore be a starting point for the present work.

Two types of confidence indices are actually presented in this milestone. The first type relates to the quality of a forecast verifying as a single value, such as near-surface temperature at a specific grid point or a climate index. The second type relates to the quality of a full forecast map, for instance in terms of spatial patterns. Both approaches are currently under investigation for seasonal forecasts of near-surface temperature at 2-m (T2M) over Europe within Task 4.3 of the present contract. After a short data description (Section 3), we address the two approaches in Sections 4 and 5 respectively. Finally, Section 5 introduces our future plans.

3. Data

We use seasonal reforecast data of near-surface temperature (T2M) from the Copernicus Climate Change Services (C3S), averaged over three-month seasons and corresponding to several lead times after initialization, namely one month (LT1, e.g DJF for November initialization), two months (LT2, e.g DJF for October initialization) and three months (LT3, e.g DJF for September initialization).

Data is retrieved from the Climate Data Store (CDS) on the 1° archiving grid. The six forecasting systems under consideration are those from CMCC, DWD, ECMWF, Météo-France, NCEP and UKMO. The ensemble sizes of each system are provided in Table 1. The common reforecast period is 1994-2016, and all reforecasts starting the 1st of each month are included in the analysis, making a sample of 12 months x 23 years = 276 start dates. Note that reforecast year 1993 is also available on the CDS but is not included due to a consistency issue in the climate trend for Météo-France. In addition, reference T2M data used for verification comes from the ERA5 reanalysis (Hersbach et al 2020) interpolated on the same 1° grid.

The focus of the confidence index is the European domain 29.5°W-40.5°E; 30.5°N-70.5°N, where sea grid points are masked. This leads to a total of 1,287 grid points. In Section 4, each grid points has its own confidence index, while Section 5 proposes to compute a single index for the whole map.

Model	CMCC	DWD	ECMWF	MF	NCEP	UKMO	Multi-model
Reforecast ensemble size	40	30	25	25	24	28	172
Real-time ensemble size	50	50	51	51	52	50	304

Table 1: Ensemble sizes of the six C3S models and the multi-model

4. Confidence index for a single-value forecast

4.1. Methodology

In this section, the focus is put on forecasting the correct tercile category of seasonal mean T2M at a specific European land grid point. The tercile categories are below normal, normal and above-normal, delimited by the 1/3 and 2/3 percentiles of a climatological distribution. The aim of the confidence index is therefore to indicate how likely the forecast is to be a “good” forecast, i.e a forecast predicting the tercile category that will eventually be observed.

For this purpose, we consider an ensemble forecast for which the tercile category predicted by each member is determined according to the climatology of the forecasting system. The tercile probabilities are obtained by taking the percentage of members within each category. The core idea is to use the probability of the most likely category, that is to say the maximum of the three probabilities, as a confidence index. This definition of the confidence index relates to the principle – as listed in the introduction – of agreement between various sources: the more the ensemble members agree, the higher the maximum probability and the higher the confidence index.

Such a confidence index needs to be validated against the actual performance of the forecast. When it comes to predicting a tercile category, the forecast performance can simply be quantified by a binary value: 1 if the forecast category matches the observed category and 0 otherwise. The observed category is provided by the ERA5 value compared to its own climatology, using the values for the same season over the 23 years of the reforecast period. As for the forecast category, it cor-

responds to the category exhibiting the maximum probability that is used to define the confidence index.

However, it is possible that more than one tercile category exhibit the same maximum probability if they share the same proportion of members (e.g 40% below normal, 40% normal and 20% above normal). For such cases, we define the “no signal” category: the confidence index and the binary verification are automatically set to zero. Note that such an operation gives the confidence index a two-tier purpose: 1) separating forecasts with and without a signal 2) quantifying confidence if the forecast exhibits a signal. As a result, the ability of the confidence index to predict forecast performance should only be assessed in the subsample of forecasts with a signal, i.e with a non-zero confidence index.

4.2. Confidence index of the raw C3S multi-model

The methodology described above is independent from the choice of the ensemble: it can be applied either to the ensemble forecast from a single modelling centre, or to a multi-model ensemble. We propose to start with the C3S multi-model comprising the CMCC, DWD, ECMWF, Météo-France, NCEP and UKMO reforecasts of 3-month average T2M at lead time 1-month. Indeed, the confidence index of such an ensemble is intended to reflect the agreement between forecasts from different modelling centres, a criterion identified by Wobus and Kalnay (1995) as the most important source of confidence. In order to compute the T2M tercile probabilities in the C3S multi-model forecasts, the members from each system are classified among the three categories according to their system’s own climatology, before being pooled together to make a 147-member ensemble. Note that the climatologies depend on the initialization month so as to remove the effect of the seasonal cycle.

The confidence index of C3S multi-model must be interpreted as the probability that the forecast T2M tercile category matches the observation, and is evaluated against the binary outcome indicating whether the forecast was correct or not. Such a framework is analogous to the verification of probabilistic predictions of a binary event, and we therefore propose similar evaluation diagnostics across the 12 monthly start dates over the full reforecast period 1994-2016.

We first assess the reliability of the confidence index, indicating whether the value of the index matches well the chance of a correct T2M forecast. This is illustrated in Figure 1a, which is similar to a usual reliability diagram, and is obtained by pooling together all 1,287 grid points in the map of Europe. Likewise, the ability of the confidence index to discriminate between correct and incorrect forecasts can be quantified with an area under a ROC curve (AUC), as shown in Figure 1b where all land grid points are pooled together again. Given one correct and one incorrect T2M forecast, the AUC is the probability that the confidence index is greater for the correct forecast than for the incorrect one (Mason and Graham, 2002). Figure 2 proposes a refined illustration of the AUC at grid point level. Note that the (0,0) point in the reliability diagram represents “no signal” forecasts for which both confidence index and binary verification are set to 0: such forecasts are removed before computing the AUCs in order to avoid increasing them artificially.

Figures 1 and 2 show that the probability of the most likely category of the C3S multi-model is a relevant confidence index: it is quite well calibrated to the chance that the forecast is correct, and is

significantly discriminant between a correct and an incorrect forecast according to a Mann-Whitney U-test. However, we might have desired higher AUC values: 0.58 means there are still a certain number of cases when a larger confidence index (e.g 0.6) comes along a wrong temperature forecast whereas a smaller confidence index (e.g 0.4) is associated to a correct temperature forecast. This limited performance of the confidence index to “forecast forecast skill” is not fully surprising, as we may presume that it is related to forecast skill itself, which is known to be modest at the seasonal time scales over Europe.

Figure 1: a) Proportion of correctly forecast tercile category by the C3S multi-model depending on the confidence index value, binned in 10 categories. The proportion of confidence indices in each bin is indicated in the histogram along the average index over the bin. Reliability and resolution components as in a Brier score are also indicated. b) Area under the ROC curve for the discrimination of correct forecasts by the confidence index. Both figures are made by pooling all grid points over Europe and considering all 12 initialization months in the 1994-2016 reforecast period.

Detection of Correct Forecasts - ROC AUC

Figure 2: Area under the ROC curve for the discrimination of correct forecasts by the confidence index at grid point level. Note that grid points in yellow correspond to an AUC below the 0.5 climatological threshold. All 12 initialization months in the 1994-2016 reforecast period are considered.

In order to dig deeper into this limited AUC value, we propose to analyse the percentage of incorrect forecasts depending on the observed T2M tercile category, as indicated in Table 2. While the outer terciles are correctly forecast about half of the time, the median tercile is missed by about 80% of the forecasts that should have predicted it. Table 3 indicates the proportion of each forecast tercile category and provides an explanation for this: set aside the “no signal” forecasts, the “normal” tercile is under-forecast compared to the “extreme” terciles while all three should be equally frequent. This is a common shortcoming of tercile probabilistic forecasts of temperature, that is explained at a theoretical level by Mason et al (2021). A potential adjustment is proposed in the next subsection.

Observed category	1 st tercile (Below normal)	2 nd tercile (Normal)	3 rd tercile (Above normal)
Percentage incorrect forecasts (%)	50.8	79.3	50.9

Table 2: Percentage of incorrect forecasts by the C3S multi-model for each tercile category.

No signal	1 st tercile (Below normal)	2 nd tercile (Normal)	3 rd tercile (Above normal)
2.6	38.0	20.8	38.6

Table 3: Percentage of C3S multi-model forecasts for each tercile category, where the forecast is based on maximum probability. No signal forecasts correspond to forecasts when the maximum probability is found for more than one tercile category.

4.3. Adjusting the “no signal” threshold

In order to have similar proportions for the three forecast tercile categories and to improve the discriminating ability of the confidence index, the proposed solution is to adjust the sample of forecasts with no seasonal signal. In Section 4.2, the only forecasts without a signal are those with two or more categories that are simultaneously the most likely. According to Table 3, this is not a very restrictive condition as it only removes $\sim 3\%$ of forecasts, a proportion which is far less than the expected proportion of “no signal” forecasts in the experience of seasonal forecasters.

An additional consideration that may lead to a “no signal” forecast is the lack of informativeness of the maximum probability, if it is too small. For instance, a forecast with probabilities 32.5%-32.5%-35% (for below, normal and above respectively) might not be deemed sharp enough, although “above normal” is the most likely category. We therefore propose to use thresholds of maximum probability (e.g 40%) to separate forecasts with and without a signal. If the maximum probability falls below the threshold, the forecast is determined to have no signal, and both confidence index and binary verification are set to zero as well. Moreover, we differentiate the threshold that must be reached for the median tercile vs the outer terciles, so as to correct the discrepancy highlighted by Table 3.

We test how the proportions of above normal, normal and below normal forecasts change when we adjust the maximum probability thresholds, and we identify the threshold combinations enabling similar proportions for the three tercile categories. A sample of these tests is indicated in Table A1 in Appendix. Similarly, Table A2 indicates the corresponding areas under the ROC curve as in Figure 1b when the thresholds is adjusted. Based on those tests, thresholds of 42% and 35% of members – for the outer and median tercile respectively – are a good compromise: the AUC is among the highest, and Table 4 shows that each tercile category is forecast about $\sim 20\%$ of the time, while $\sim 40\%$ of forecasts are considered to have no signal. Both thresholds could still be increased to improve the AUC, but this would either keep uneven proportions between normal and extreme terciles, and/or leave an unreasonably small number of forecasts with a signal.

No signal	1 st tercile (Below normal)	2 nd tercile (Normal)	3 rd tercile (Above normal)
41.8	19.4	19.1	19.7

Table 4: Percentage of C3S multi-model forecasts for each tercile category, where the forecast is based on maximum probability. The thresholds to exclude forecasts without a signal are set to 0.42 for outer terciles and 0.35 for the normal tercile.

Figures 3 and 4 propose a comparative evaluation of the confidence index, with and without threshold adjustment (i.e results in Section 4.2). The adjusted thresholds are set to 42% and 35% for outer and normal terciles respectively. As shown by the reliability diagram, the threshold adjustment results in a slight decrease in reliability of the confidence index: while the probabilities of a correct forecast do not change for high confidence index values not affected by thresholding, the confidence index becomes more overconfident when its values are low (below 50%). However, the thresholds bring an increase in discrimination between correct and incorrect forecasts: even though this increase seems modest when considering all grid points (0.61 vs 0.58), some local improvements are more notable, e.g over Western Europe (see Figure 4 vs Figure 2). The threshold adjustment therefore results in a trade-off between reliability and discrimination/resolution of the confidence index.

Figure 3: Same as Figure 1 when the thresholds to separate forecasts with and without a signal are adjusted to maximum probabilities of 42% for the outer terciles and 35% for the normal tercile. Results from Figure 1 with the default 1/3-1/3 thresholds are put in grey for comparison.

Figure 4: Same as Figure 2 when the thresholds to separate forecasts with and without a signal are adjusted to maximum probabilities of 42% for the outer terciles and 35% for the normal tercile.

4.4. Including forecast stability

So far, the proposed confidence index only relies on the agreement among a large number of members initialized at the same date. In line with the principles stated in introduction, we also propose to take into account the stability of consecutive forecasts (valid for the same period) as another source of confidence. To do so, we simply include forecasts of the seasonal anomalies of T2M at lead times 2 and 3 months within the C3S multi-model, besides those at lead time 1-month. Note that the climatology to define tercile categories in the reforecasts therefore depends on the forecasting system and the initialization month but also the lead time. The resulting ensemble is $172 \times 3 = 516$ members and we adopt the same approach as before to define and evaluate the confidence index.

In order to get results that are comparable the previous section, we decide to adjust the “no signal” thresholds such that the proportions remain similar to those in Table 5. This leads to a switch from thresholds 42% and 35% to thresholds 41%-33% thresholds for the outer and normal terciles.

The evaluation of the confidence index is provided in Figures 5 and 6. The comparison with the previous results based only on lead time 1-month shows that including the lead time 2 and 3-months in the multi-model leads to virtually no difference: the confidence index remains similarly reliable (comparison of reliability component between Figures 3a and 5a) and similarly discriminant (comparison of AUC between Figures 3b and 5b).

Figure 5: Same as Figure 3 when previous forecasts at lead times 2 and 3 months (LT2 and LT3) are also included. Thresholds to define no signal forecasts have been set to 41% for outer terciles and 33% for normal tercile. Results from Figure 3 are put in grey as a reminder.

Detection of Correct Forecasts - ROC AUC

Figure 6: Same as Figure 4 when the forecasts at lead times 2 and 3 months are also included. Thresholds to define no signal forecasts have been set to 41% for outer terciles and 33% for normal tercile.

4.5. Accounting for the climate trend

All the previous confidence indices of T2M seasonal forecasts have been evaluated across the 1994-2016 period without removal of the warming trend. However, a non-negligible part of the signal in the forecasts of T2M seasonal anomalies comes from this trend. The aim of this subsection is to analyse whether the confidence index is still relevant to indicate confidence in the forecasts of the unforced climate variability. For this purpose, the same analysis as in Section 4.3 (i.e C3S multi-model with lead time 1-month) is carried out on the T2M tercile categories in seasonal forecasts and ERA5 reference data after removal of a linear trend over the years 1994-2016. Note that the trend was computed separately for each forecasting system and initialization month. To keep similar proportions of forecast categories as in Table 5 (i.e ~ 40% for no signal, ~20% for below normal, normal and above normal), maximum probability thresholds are modified to 40% (instead of 42%) for outer terciles, and kept to 35% for normal terciles.

Figures 7 and 8 illustrate that the confidence index for data with a removed climate trend becomes overconfident for its highest values, hence a loss in reliability. It is also less discriminant between correct and incorrect forecast (AUC decreases from 0.61 to 0.58). However, this decrease of quality of the confidence index is small and the proposed approach may be considered valid after removing the climate trend.

Figure 7: Same as Figure 3 when the confidence index at lead time 1 month is computed after detrending of T2M data. Results from Figure 3 without detrending are put in grey as a reminder. Thresholds to define no signal forecasts have been set to 40% for outer terciles and 35% for normal tercile.

Detection of Correct Forecasts - ROC AUC

Figure 8: Same as Figure 4 when the confidence index at lead time 1 month is computed after detrending of T2M data. Thresholds to define no signal forecasts have been set to 40% for outer terciles and 35% for normal tercile.

4.6. Summary

This section proposes the definition of a confidence index for the ensemble forecast of a single-value parameter, in that case T2M seasonal anomalies at grid point level. The approach is based on the forecast probabilities of the tercile categories relative to climatology, and the confidence index simply corresponds to the maximum of the three probabilities in the C3S multi-model forecast. This confidence index has been confronted to a binary verification approach when the forecast scores 1 if the most likely category is observed, and 0 otherwise. Although far from perfect, such a confidence index appears to be reasonably reliable in indicating the chance that a forecast is correct, and reasonably good at discriminating a correct and an incorrect forecast.

Incremental adjustments have been attempted to make the confidence index even more informative. A first adjustment that leads to a better ability of the confidence index to “forecast forecast skill” is not a modification of the index itself, but a restriction of the sample of forecasts where it is applied, through the definition of “no signal” forecasts. Although this might seem a trivial operation, indicating forecasts without a signal is meaningful in the context of seasonal forecast bulletins. A second adjustment is to include previous forecasts in the ensemble before computing the confidence index. However, such an enrichment of the multi-model does not necessarily yield a better

index. Finally, it should be stressed that when it comes to near-surface temperature, the warming trend is responsible for some of the performance of the confidence index.

5. Confidence index for a spatial field

This section is dedicated to expressing confidence in the seasonal forecast of a map of near-surface temperature anomalies, with an application to Europe. As in the previous section, only land grid points are kept. Similarly, the confidence index to be defined must be confronted to the performance of the forecast, with an appropriate forecast verification metric for the full spatial field.

5.1. Aggregating confidence indices at grid-point level

A first approach is to use the confidence index introduced in Section 4, to compute it at every grid point and to summarize the information at the scale of the map. For this purpose, we simply take the average of the confidence indices over all grid points. The confidence indices for spatial averaging are those of Figures 3 and 4, with thresholds of 42% and 35% maximum probability to exclude no signal forecasts for outer and normal terciles respectively. Figure 9 compares this average confidence index against the proportion of grid points in the map for which the tercile category is correctly forecast. Note that grid points where there is no forecast signal are also included in the computations: these grid points tend to lower the average confidence index because it is set to zero at those locations, and they also lower the ratio of correct forecasts because they are incorrect by definition. As a result, the strong relationship exhibited by Figure 9 – between average confidence index and proportion of correct grid points over Europe – is partly artificial, but the figure confirms that summarizing confidence through a simple averaging gives an overview of the expected forecast quality at the European scale, while keeping the same framework as in Section 4.

Figure 9: Scatter plot of the proportion of grid points over Europe with a correctly forecast tercile category in the C3S multi-model at lead time 1 month as in Section 4.3, against the spatial average of the confidence indices. Each dot represents one reforecast date among the 12 initializations in 1994-2016 (276 values). The linear regression of the scatter plot is indicated in red.

5.2. Exploiting predictable patterns

A second approach for confidence in a spatial field that will also be explored is to see whether the forecast projects strongly on patterns that the forecasting system tends to predict more correctly. Several methods to identify such patterns have been tested at shorter time scales, for instance by Branstator et al (1993) or Renwick and Wallace (1995). The technique for which we made preliminary tests so far is called Predictable Component Analysis (PrCA) and was first introduced by Déqué (1988). It identifies patterns for which the mean square error over the reforecast period, used as the training set, is minimum.

In order to implement it, we took the forecast maps of the ensemble mean T2M anomalies over Europe for the full 1994-2016 reforecasts (all initialization months included) and their corresponding T2M anomaly maps in ERA5. A preliminary step is to reduce the dimension from 1,287 grid points to a limited number of EOFs based on the reference data ERA5. Both forecast and ERA5 anomaly maps are projected onto these EOFs and the principal components are normalized by their

standard deviation. The variance-covariance matrix of the forecast error among the principal components can be decomposed into as many eigenvectors and eigenvalues as the number of EOFs retained. The eigenvectors are the predictable patterns, and the eigenvalues are the mean square errors of the forecast for the projection against each pattern. As a result, the eigenvector with the lowest eigenvalue is the most predictable component, and so on.

The *a priori* confidence index of a given forecast uses the coordinates of the forecast in the orthonormal basis of predictable patterns. The confidence index is actually obtained through a weighted average of eigenvalues, where the weights are these squared coordinates. The index therefore corresponds to an expected mean square error of the forecast over the full spatial map: as the forecast projects more strongly on the most predictable patterns, the expected error decreases. In order to make it a 0-to-1 confidence index, it is eventually rescaled using the highest and lowest eigenvalues, similar to a skill score.

Figure 10 illustrates the implementation of such a confidence index for the Météo-France reforecast, when 6 EOFs are initially retained to decompose the variance of T2M anomalies over Europe, therefore keeping 87.5 % of variance and leading to 6 predictable patterns. The evaluation of the confidence index against the actual forecast skill, as measured by Anomaly Correlation Coefficient, is shown in Figure 11. Figure 11 shows that there is relationship between the *a priori* index and the actual ability to forecast the spatial pattern of T2M anomalies: although weak, the fitted linear relationship is noteworthy, and more specifically we notice that high values of the confidence index (e.g. > 0.8) are almost always associated with high ACCs.

Forecast amplitude:
 $|F|^2 = \alpha_1^2 + \alpha_2^2 + \alpha_3^2 + \alpha_4^2 + \alpha_5^2 + \alpha_6^2$

Forecast expected Mean Square Error:
 $E^2 = \lambda_1^2 \alpha_1^2 + \lambda_2^2 \alpha_2^2 + \lambda_3^2 \alpha_3^2 + \lambda_4^2 \alpha_4^2 + \lambda_5^2 \alpha_5^2 + \lambda_6^2 \alpha_6^2$

Rescale MSE = confidence index in [0,1]:

$$\frac{E^2 - \lambda_6^2 |F|^2}{\lambda_1^2 |F|^2 - \lambda_6^2 |F|^2}$$

Figure 10: Summary of the computation of the T2M confidence index based on predictable components (PrC), determined from the Météo-France 1994-2016 reforecasts (all months) against ERA5 in the subspace of the first 6 ERA5 EOFs.

Note that this confidence index has a major flaw: as it only relies on predefined predictable patterns computed on the reforecast period, it lacks flexibility in a real-time context. For instance, we notice in Figure 11 that many reforecasts exhibit a low confidence index but high ACC values. It means that these forecasts project more strongly on less predictable patterns, that nonetheless turned out to be close to the observations. A refinement to improve the index could be to take into account both the projection on predictable patterns and the agreement among models.

Moreover, the example shown here is for the Météo-France system only, because the relationship between confidence index and ACC was quite illustrative, while it was less convincing for other models or with the multi-model (not shown). Finally, although predictable component analysis optimizes mean square error, the relationship between the confidence index and the actual mean

square error is weaker than with ACC (not shown): this points to the fact that a confidence index has more or less value depending on which aspect of forecast skill we are interested in.

Figure 11: Scatter plot of the Anomaly Correlation Coefficient of seasonal-mean T2M over Europe in Météo-France reforecasts (1994-2016, all initialization months) at lead time 1 month, against the confidence index based on Predictable Component Analysis. Each dot represents one reforecast date (276 values). The linear regression of the scatter plot is indicated in red.

6. Future plans

This milestone has provided an overview of the various methodologies that we have started exploring so far to define a confidence index for seasonal forecasts of climate conditions over Europe. A first methodology applies to forecasts of tercile categories for a single parameter, while the second relates to the overall quality of the predicted spatial pattern. It is likely that within Task 4.3 we will actually propose a final version of the two approaches, because they answer two different questions that a user may ask when facing a real-time seasonal forecast. Note that it will therefore be necessary to name them appropriately in order to avoid confusion with the same “confidence index” term.

Our near-term plans for the single-value confidence index include:

- 1) Clarifying the relationship between the forecast performance and the confidence index ability to “forecast forecast skill”. Some characteristics, such as the reliability of the confidence index in predicting correct forecasts, are presumably with the reliability of the forecast itself and this should be explored.
- 2) Implementing the approach on other parameters: precipitation at grid point level, box-averaged temperature and precipitation, indices representing the atmospheric circulation (e.g North Atlantic Oscillation, East Atlantic mode, Scandinavian Blocking)
- 3) Testing the approach in a real-time setting to get a feel of how informative such an index could be (e.g. how does an index value of 0.5 translate in terms of usability of forecast information)

Our near-term plans for the spatial confidence index include:

- 1) Refining the predictable component analysis approach (e.g combining the predictable component analysis with information about agreement among models) and/or testing alternative methodologies such as canonical correlation analysis (see Renwick and Wallace, 1995).
- 2) Testing approaches to “forecast forecast skill” based on spatial agreement (i.e correlation) among members and models, as in Kalnay and Dalcher (1987).
- 3) Testing approaches to “forecast forecast skill” using regression on several aspects of the forecasts as in Palmer and Molteni (1991) or Wobus and Kalnay (1995).
- 4) Implementing the approaches on other variables: precipitation and geopotential at 500 hPa.

Finally, it was envisioned in the proposal for Task 4.3 to leverage the presence of strong physical drivers of seasonal predictability (e.g tropical sea surface temperature) as an additional and intermittent source of confidence. Including those physical drivers in the previous approaches (relying only on statistics so far) will be considered, although their inclusion is not straightforward. The presumably easiest way to do it is to use composite probabilities for specific states of the driver in the

climatological record, and consider them as another forecast in the multi-model pool. However, it cannot be excluded that all the confidence that can be gained from physical drivers already reflects in characteristics such as agreement between models and that adding them explicitly will not provide a better prediction of the expected forecast skill.

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8. Appendix

Thesholds (Outer – Normal)	Percentage of forecast tercile categories			
	No signal	1 st tercile (Be- low normal)	2 nd tercile (Normal)	3 rd tercile (Above normal)
1/3 – 1/3	2.6	38.0	20.8	38.6
0.4 – 1/3	28.5	25.0	20.8	25.6
0.42 – 1/3	40.1	19.4	20.8	19.7
0.42 – 0.35	41.8	19.4	19.1	19.7
0.43 – 0.35	44.4	18.1	19.1	18.4
0.44 – 0.36	45.7	18.1	17.8	18.4

Table A1: Percentage of C3S multi-model forecasts for each tercile category, depending on various thresholds used to exclude forecasts without a signal. The retained solution (42%-35%) is in bold red.

		Normal tercile probability threshold				
		1/3	0.35	0.36	0.37	0.38
	1/3	0.579	0.578	0.576	0.573	0.570
	0.35	0.580	0.578	0.577	0.573	0.570
	0.36	0.580	0.579	0.577	0.573	0.568
	0.37	0.583	0.582	0.580	0.575	0.569
	0.38	0.588	0.586	0.584	0.579	0.572

Outer ter- cile prob- ability threshold	0.39	0.595	0.593	0.592	0.587	0.579
	0.4	0.599	0.597	0.595	0.591	0.583
	0.41	0.607	0.606	0.604	0.600	0.594
	0.42	0.615	0.615	0.613	0.610	0.604
	0.43	0.619	0.619	0.617	0.614	0.609
	0.44	0.626	0.626	0.625	0.623	0.619
	0.45	0.632	0.632	0.632	0.631	0.627

Table A2: Area under the ROC curve (as in Figure 1b) for the detection of correct forecasts with the confidence index, depending on the adjusted thresholds of maximum probability to exclude forecasts without a signal. Thresholds are differentiated between outer terciles (rows) and the normal tercile (columns). The retained solution (42%-35%) is in bold red.

